

People-Centred Transformation of Cultural Heritage Buildings

Inherit

A Social Science and Multi-Stakeholder Framework for Sustainability

The challenge

The sustainable transformation of cultural heritage buildings goes beyond technical solutions; it requires inclusive, participatory approaches that **engage local stakeholders and foster social innovation**. Cultural significance, complex social dynamics and competing interests among authorities, owners, users, experts and communities must be addressed, or interventions risk low acceptance and limited long-term impact.

This socially informed framework responds to this gap by integrating social science evidence and structured stakeholder engagement into decision-making processes for cultural heritage buildings.

Funded by
the European Union

The impact

This integrated approach supports more inclusive governance models and socially informed policies for cultural heritage buildings, increasing local engagement and context-specific solutions. It also serves as a transferable reference framework that can be applied beyond individual projects, contributing to **long-term knowledge transfer and capacity building** in the field of sustainable cultural heritage. The framework builds on the insights gathered through the analysis of the eight pilot sites of the INHERIT project, ensuring its evidence base and practical applicability.

Core framework's principles

Renovating with a social focus:

Addressing the climate crisis in the context of cultural heritage buildings requires a systematic methodology that combines social, scientific and technological processes. Through multi-stakeholder engagement and co-creation, this approach ensures that technical solutions are aligned with local values and cultural identity.

Participatory models:

The active involvement of communities, authorities, experts and cultural players across all stages of decision-making ensures that preservation or renovation efforts align with the needs and priorities of the community. Measures such as educational methods, raising awareness, co-creation laboratories, e-learning packages and policy dialogues strengthen social sustainability and acceptance.

New European Bauhaus (NEB) as enabling initiative:

The New European Bauhaus provides a policy and operational framework that supports the sustainable, inclusive and aesthetically sensitive transformation of cultural heritage buildings.

Blueprint for co-creating user scenarios:

Co-creating user scenarios is essential to ensure that services respond to real-world needs, expectations and experiences of stakeholders. This process relies on the identification of user stories and scenarios to explore how different users interact with solutions, helping determine requirements, generate ideas and guide development.

The methodology has three phases:

1. collecting user stories and user requirements,
2. co-designing user-friendly environments, and
3. refining usability, to ensure solutions that are practical, accessible and aligned with user needs.

Putting the framework into practice

1. Mapping societal enablers

Mapping societal enablers is essential for understanding the conditions that facilitate or hinder stakeholder engagement, policy implementation, and long-term cultural heritage resilience. Societal enablers include social actors, policies, financial mechanisms and participatory processes that support community-driven and sustainable interventions. Combining policy analysis, desk research and participatory workshops, the process identifies key actors, mechanisms and contextual factors such as institutional support, community participation, financial accessibility and regulatory flexibility.

2. Social life cycle analysis (S-LCA)

S-LCA is a structured assessment tool used to collect qualitative and quantitative data on social inclusiveness, economic efficiency and environmental responsibility at pilot sites. Data are collected through surveys and in-depth expert interviews at three stages of implementation, allowing comparative analysis over time. Based on recognised standards and literature, a set of indicators evaluates governance, management practices and stakeholder engagement. The results inform recommendations to improve actor involvement in heritage governance and feed into decision-support services and policy guidance, strengthening the overall societal impact of interventions.

3. Social labs

The project puts this framework into practice through the implementation of social labs, which serve as platforms for stakeholder engagement and co-creation. These labs facilitate workshops and discussions that bring together diverse participants – and therefore perspectives – to collaboratively explore heritage management challenges and develop innovative solutions. This participatory process leads to more relevant and effective heritage interventions and, ultimately, to the long-term sustainability of heritage sites.

Conclusion

The integration of a social science and multi-stakeholder framework is key in promoting sustainable management of cultural heritage sites. Its focus on inclusivity, co-creation, and participatory decision-making enables people-centred, culturally sensitive, and viable transformation of heritage buildings. The practical implementation of this framework through Social Labs and the S-LCA not only enhances the effectiveness of heritage interventions but also sets a precedent for future projects aiming to balance social responsibility with cultural preservation.

The full study "[Active societal participation & enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment](#)" is available on the [INHERIT website](#).

Authors:

Gioele Racca (ICLEI), Dimitra Aglamisi (UPCR)

Graphic Design: Lorenzo Cannella (ICONS)

Deliverable authors:

Gioele Racca (ICLEI); Rexhina Merkohitaj; Pamela Bartar; Philipp Brugner (ZSI); Petra Vučetić Osonjački (REGEA); Antonia Vronti (SLG)

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For questions and
additional information
contact us at:

info@inheritproject.eu